

Unveiling Innovation Potential of Circular Approaches
in Automotive Electronics and Beyond

Methodology for net impact measurement of functional electronics integration

Grant Agreement number: 101070169
Project acronym: UNICORN
Project title: Unveiling Innovation Potential of Circular Approaches in Automotive Electronics and Beyond

Authors: Jana Deckers, Karolien Peeters, Stefanie De Smet, Pieter Willot, VITO

Publication Date: 30.08.2025

Funded by the
European Union

Table of contents

1	Executive summary	5
2	Introduction	8
2.1	UNICORN project	8
2.2	Aim and purpose of the net impact assessment methodology.....	8
2.3	Document scope and outline	9
3	Selection of the methodology for net impact assessment	10
3.1	Context and requirements for the methodology	10
3.1.1	<i>Context of UNICORN and transformation pathways</i>	10
3.1.2	<i>Requirements for the net impact assessment methodology</i>	12
3.2	Overview of existing relevant standards and methodologies, including metrics...12	
3.2.1	<i>Environmental impact assessment methodologies</i>	12
3.2.2	Methodologies for circularity assessment.....	14
3.3	Selection of methodologies and metrics.....	16
4	Concepts.....	18
4.1	Functional electronics solution	18
4.2	Use case example	18
4.3	Assessment concepts according to the EGDC method and the PEF method.....19	
4.3.1	Scenario.....	19
4.3.2	Solution description & assessment boundary (system boundaries)	19
4.3.3	Functional unit.....	20
4.3.4	Implementation context	20
4.4	Components of a net carbon impact assessment.....	20
4.4.1	First order effects	20
4.4.2	Second order effects	21
4.4.3	Higher order effects.....	21
4.4.4	Rebound effects.....	21
5	Assessing the net impact of the integration of functional electronics in a specific implementation context.....	22
5.1	Assessment steps.....	22
5.2	Defining the Assessment (Goal and scope)	24
5.2.1	Assessment objective (Goal).....	24
5.2.2	Solution description & boundary.....	25
5.2.3	Functional unit.....	26
5.2.4	Assessment boundary.....	27
5.2.5	Reference scenario definition	31
5.3	Identifying effects.....	32
5.3.1	Identifying reference and solution scenario activities and emission sources....	32
5.3.2	Mapping effects in a consequence tree	33

5.4	Calculating effects	35
5.4.1	Identify relevant effects (Estimating the relative magnitude of effects).....	35
5.4.2	Data Collection.....	35
5.4.3	First order effects	35
5.4.4	Second order effects	36
5.4.5	Higher order effects.....	36
5.5	Net impact calculation.....	36
5.5.1	Net environmental impact calculation	36
5.5.2	Circularity assessment	39
5.6	Uncertainty and Sensitivity Analysis.....	40
5.7	Critical Review	40
5.8	Recalculation	40
5.9	Consideration of other environmental impacts	40
6	References.....	41
7	Annexes	43
7.1	Annex 1: The environmental impact categories of the Product Environmental Footprint methodology	43
7.2	Annex 2: Optional indicators	45
7.3	Annex 3: List of critical raw materials (European Commission, 2023)	47

List of Acronyms

5E	Federating European Electronics Ecosystems for Competitive Electronics Industries
CA	Circularity Assessment
CCI	Circular Cars Initiative
CE	Circular Economy
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CTI	Circular Transition Indicators
EGDC	The European Green Digital Coalition
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
ETSI TC EE	European Telecommunications Standards Institute Technical Committee Environmental Engineering
EU	European Union
FE	Functional Electronic
GHG	Greenhouse gas
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
ITU-T	International Telecommunication Union – Telecommunication Standardisation Sector
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MCI	Material Circularity Indicator
NCIA	Net Carbon Impact Assessment
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
SOC	State of Charge
SOH	State of Health
SOT	State of Temperature
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Kévin Le Blévennec for his valuable contributions in reviewing and enhancing the introduction and selection of the methodology sections.

Executive summary

The methodology “**Net Impact Measurement for Functional Electronics Integration**” developed within the framework of the Horizon Europe project UNICORN, outlines a comprehensive approach to assess different **environmental and circularity aspects** of the integration of functional electronics into various application. The methodology primarily focuses on the **automotive sector but can be applied in a sector-agnostic manner**. This methodology aims to capture both **positive and negative effects** including all direct and indirect effects of the integration, comparing scenarios with and without functional electronics (FE) integration.

The methodology enables UNICORN consortium partners and other stakeholder in the functional electronics sector to evaluate and enhance the environmental and circularity performance of their innovations and solutions. **The framework supports the overarching goal of achieving net impact across four pathways: energy (and product) decarbonisation, material circularity, lifetime optimisation and utilisation improvement.**

Within the context of the UNICORN project, and in alignment with the EU funded 5E project¹, **a FE solution is defined as a system that integrates advanced functionalities with physical components, extending beyond traditional electronics to deliver specific services to users.** As transversal enablers of the EU digital transition, functional electronics can support and advance the green transition. However, the digital transition and the integration of electronics in an ever-increasing diversity of products and market segments can also lead to, amongst others, increased energy demand, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, resource use and electronic waste generation which should be avoided. **The proposed methodology facilitates the identification of FE solutions that can achieve a net positive impact by effectively reducing environmental burdens and considering multiple environmental aspects and the trade-offs between carbon footprint, material circularity and other impacts.**

The document provides a detailed framework for assessing the net impact of functional electronics, leveraging existing methodologies and standards such as the European Green Digital Coalition's (EGDC) Net Carbon Impact Assessment, the ISO 14044 and Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) for Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) and ISO 59020 standard for circularity assessment to the specific context of functional electronics. The document outlines relevant methods and standards and provides the rationale behind the selection of the Net Carbon Impact Assessment methodology complemented with ISO and PEF standards for LCA and the ISO 59020 standard (Chapter 3). Figure 0.1 illustrates that the **Net Impact Assessment is supported by a Life Cycle Assessment and Circularity assessment.**

In line with the EGDC methodology, this methodology introduces the necessary assessment concepts and components (Chapter 4). The methodology requires the definition of **a reference scenario and solution scenario**. The reference scenario represents the situation without implementing the solution, where the solution scenario defines the situation where the functional electronics solution is implemented. The effects of the implementation of functional electronics are mapped in a consequence tree and consist of **first order effects, second order effects and higher order effects**. First order effects are the life cycle impacts resulting directly from the components of the solution. Second order effects are the indirect impacts that arise from changes to the reference activities due to the deployment and use of the solution. Higher order effects are indirect impacts that arise as a consequence of second order effects, often following behavioural or structural changes such as shifts in consumption patterns, lifestyles, and value systems.

¹ 5E - Federating European Electronics Ecosystems for Competitive Electronics Industries. Grant Agreement 825113. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825113>

Figure 0.1: overview of the different steps of a net impact assessment (modified from EGDC's Net Carbon Impact Assessment steps), life cycle assessment (LCA) according to ISO 14040/44 standards and circularity assessment (CA) according to ISO 59020

After calculating the impacts from first, second, and higher-order effects, by means of a life cycle assessment, the net impact of the solution can be determined per environmental impact category. Indeed, the methodology requires the calculation of multiple environmental aspects, not only the carbon footprint. The net impact of environmental aspect X for the functional unit (FU) of the assessment is calculated as:

$$Net\ Impact_{FU, X} = Reference\ scenario\ X - [\Sigma 1st\ Order\ Effects\ X + \Sigma 2nd\ Order\ Effects\ X + \Sigma Higher\ Order\ Effects\ X]$$

Figure 0.2 provides an illustrative example a net impact calculation in the format of a Waterfall graph. The environmental aspects considered in the assessment are aggregated in a single score (expressed in Points (Pt)). In this example, the implementation of the Functional Electronic (FE) solution scenario results in a reduction of the environmental impact compared to the reference scenario.

Figure 0.2: Illustrative example of a net environmental impact calculation

This document outlines the assessment steps, from defining the assessment to calculation of the effects and performances, and illustrates the methodology using a use case example. It provides guidance on the selection of environmental and circularity metrics to measure the net impact of functional electronics (Chapter 5).

1 Introduction

Functional electronics can play a crucial role in supporting the green transition towards a sustainable economy. To comprehensively evaluate their environmental impact and circularity performance, a robust methodology is essential. The methodology proposed in this document has been developed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project UNICORN².

1.1 UNICORN project

To strengthen the European Union's (EU) global competitiveness and resilience, the European Commission's updated Industrial Strategy³ calls for accelerating the green and digital (twin) transitions of key European ecosystems. In that perspective and funded under the call 'HORIZON-CL4-2021 Digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the Green Deal' and more specifically the topic 'Functional electronics for green and circular economy', the UNICORN project aims to support the development of functional electronics for accelerating the transition of the automotive industry to a circular economy. It foresees functional electronics as an enabler and catalyser of Europe's mobility's twin transition.

At the convergence of unconventional nano-electronics, flexible, organic & printed electronics and electronic smart systems, the term 'Functional Electronics' was introduced as part of the EU-funded project 5E⁴ in 2020. It encompasses the ever-increasing capability to integrate key digital technologies with cognitive functions, shifting from purely physical integration to functional integration⁵.

The UNICORN project has been set up to support fundamental systemic changes throughout the automotive electronics value chain. It aims to demonstrate a capability to design and develop innovative green and circular technologies for automotive electronics, based on four electronic systems taken from industrial use cases for a battery casing, a dashboard, a seat/door system and a tire. These functional electronics solutions (1) encompass lightweight, low impact and/or bio-based materials for (flexible) substrates, films, encapsulation, inks, solvents, adhesives and flat cabling and interconnects; 2) validate resource/energy efficient, net shape, additive, printing, encapsulating and (reversible) bonding manufacturing processes for circuitry, sensors, gauges, antennas, interconnects; and 3) implement design for material circularity via reversible design, modularity, form factors to increase disassembly and recovery of valuable materials.

1.2 Aim and purpose of the net impact assessment methodology

It is commonly acknowledged that the digital transition can support and accelerate the green transition. As transversal enablers of the EU digital transition, functional electronics can play a crucial role. However, the digital transition and this penetration of electronic devices in ever-increasing diversity of products and market-segments can also lead to harmful effects in terms of energy demand, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, resource use and electronic waste generation that should be avoided.

To comprehensively evaluate the environmental and circularity impacts and ensure that the integration of functional electronics leads to environmental benefits, a robust assessment methodology is essential. This methodology should capture both positive and negative effects, including all direct and indirect effects of the integration. Such net impact assessment should compare scenarios with and without functional electronics integration within the same boundary.

² *Unveiling Innovation Potential of Circular Approaches in Automotive Electronics and Beyond* - GA 101070169 - <https://project-unicorn.eu/>

³ https://commission.europa.eu/document/9ab0244c-6ca3-4b11-bef9-422c7eb34f39_en

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825113>

⁵ Further definition is provided in section 4.1

The objective of this report is to develop a methodological assessment framework for assessing the net impacts of functional electronics integration⁶. This framework shall also be used in the UNICORN Project in order to assess the environmental and circularity performance of the Use Cases, so it is an important milestone in the project towards generating positive environmental impact.

The Net Impact Assessment encompasses a comprehensive evaluation of the direct and indirect environmental impacts - hereafter referred to as net environmental impact assessment - and the circularity performance of functional electronics. Since this approach considers multiple environmental aspects and potential trade-offs between environmental and circularity performance the methodology is collectively referred to as Net Impact Assessment.

1.3 Document scope and outline

The developed methodology allows to identify functional electronics solutions that can deliver a net positive impact by reducing environmental impacts in a defined implementation context. Although the UNICORN project is focusing on the integration of functional electronics in the automotive sector, the developed methodology is sector-agnostic and is suited for application in other sectors and implementation contexts. The assessment methodology presented in this document focusses on environmental and circularity impact. Social impacts are not considered.

The intended users of this methodology are primarily the partners of the UNICORN consortium, and by extension, other manufacturers or users of functional electronics. Users of this methodology are assumed to have knowledge of life cycle assessment (LCA) principles.

Chapter 3 summarises the literature review by presenting an overview of relevant methodologies and standards. It also explains the rationale for selecting and adapting the most appropriate methodology. As anticipated during UNICORN proposal stage, the developed methodology is primarily based on the methodology proposed by the European Green Digital Coalition (EGDC) for 'Net Carbon Impact Assessment for ICT Solutions' (EGDC, 2024).

Chapter 4 defines relevant concepts to this methodological assessment framework. It defines functional electronics and presents the selected use case to instantiate the assessment framework. In line with the EGDC methodology, it introduces the necessary assessment concepts and components including scenarios definition, comparison and integration effects.

Chapter 5 offers an illustrated guidance on the application of the methodology. It provides a description of the assessment steps including the definition of the assessment, the identification of effects, the calculation, and additional relevant steps for the net impact assessment.

Chapters 4 and 5 of this document are related to the EGDC document titled: 'Net Carbon Impact Assessment Methodology for ICT Solutions', (EGDC, 2024). These chapters follow the same structure as Chapters 2 and 3 of the EGDC document respectively. This document is recommended to be read in parallel with the EGDC methodology to provide optimal insight and guidance.

⁶ The methodology outlined in this document will be applied during the execution of the UNICORN project. If necessary, this methodology document will be updated based on the findings from the test cases conducted within the UNICORN project.

2 Selection of the methodology for net impact assessment

2.1 Context and requirements for the methodology

2.1.1 Context of UNICORN and transformation pathways

The EU aims to transition to a circular economy to reduce pressure on natural resources, create sustainable growth and jobs, and to achieve the EU's 2050 climate neutrality target as well as halt biodiversity loss⁷. This circular economy transition is also one of the six environmental objectives⁸ of the EU Taxonomy, created to qualify an economic activity as environmentally sustainable and direct investments towards sustainable projects and activities.

Targeting a specific sector and with the overarching goal to achieve an automobility system that is convenient, affordable and firmly grounded within a 1.5°C climate scenario by 2030, The World Economic Forum and the World Business Council for Sustainable Development jointly formed the Circular Cars Initiative (CCI) in 2020. As part of this initiative, a vision for a 'circular car'⁹ as a core of a low carbon mobility system was defined together with a five-level taxonomy for monitoring the progress and achieving this visionary ambition. To accelerate the transition from today's "linear" scenario (level 1) to a "circular" one (level 5), 4 main transformation pathways were identified, see Figure 1: energy decarbonisation, material circularity, lifetime optimisation and utilisation improvement.

⁷ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy_en

⁸ Together with climate change mitigation, climate change adaptation, sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, pollution prevention and control and protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems

⁹ The term "circular car" refers to a theoretical vehicle that has maximised materials efficiency. This vehicle would produce zero materials waste and zero pollution during manufacture, usage and disposal – which differentiates it from today's zero-emission vehicles. While cars may never be fully "circular", the automotive industry can significantly increase its degree of circularity. Doing so has the potential to deliver economic, societal and ecological dividends.

Figure 1: Circularity levels and transformation pathways (CCI, ?)

This vision for a ‘circular car’ and these 4 transformation pathways were used to lay down the foundations of the UNICORN project and set circularity ambition of selected use-cases (see section 1.1).

Although these transformation pathways were defined in the context of sustainable mobility, they are considered as relevant for other sectors as well. A balanced approach to all four pathways is important. Investing heavily in only one pathway, such as energy and product decarbonisation, misses out on opportunities of other pathways and limits improvements. Additionally, these circular strategies are not inherently sustainable and apply to different levels (material, product, processes, business models). The double benefit of improving both carbon footprint and resource efficiency should be appropriately considered – making utilisation improvement, lifetime extension and materials circularity ultimately complementary to energy and product decarbonisation.

2.1.2 Requirements for the net impact assessment methodology

The requirements for a net impact assessment methodology that supports the objectives of the UNICORN project and the functional electronics sector are defined as follows:

1. Should be able to measure the net impact of four main transformation pathways:
 - ENERGY (AND PRODUCT) DECARBONISATION: achieving net-zero carbon emissions across the whole life cycle
 - MATERIAL CIRCULARITY: enabling resource recovery and closing material loops
 - LIFETIME OPTIMISATION: increasing lifetime of systems/use cases and of their components
 - UTILISATION IMPROVEMENT: ensuring efficient use of systems;
2. Should rely as much as possible on relevant existing standards and methodologies;
3. Applies relevant 'metrics' to assess whether it is worthwhile to integrate functional electronics in a specific use case. Are there trade-offs between the carbon footprint of functional electronics and their performance on other environmental aspects, and by extension, the circularity of functional electronics? While UNICORN's main focus is on optimisation and material circularity, the methodology should provide insights into a potential shift of burdens to other environmental aspects when optimising carbon emissions and material circularity;
4. Should be able to capture the benefits of the implementation of functional electronics;
5. Should be feasible and attractive for industry to apply the methodology.

2.2 Overview of existing relevant standards and methodologies, including metrics

This section provides a summary of the literature review on methodologies and standards for measuring the net impact of functional electronics. It includes a short description of each relevant method or standard, including an overview of the metrics proposed by the method or standard. The relevant methodologies are divided into two main categories. The first category includes methodologies for measuring environmental impacts, being life cycle assessment (LCA) methodologies. Special attention is given to methodologies from sectors closely related to the functional electronics sector, particularly those that are able to capture the benefits of the integration of electronics. The second category encompasses methodologies designed to assess the effects of circular economy measures.

2.2.1 Environmental impact assessment methodologies

2.2.1.1 ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 on Life Cycle Assessment (ISO, 2006)

ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 are key international standards for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), providing guidelines and requirements for conducting environmental assessments of products and processes.

ISO 14040: This standard outlines the principles and framework for LCA, detailing four main phases: (1) Goal and Scope Definition, where the purpose, system boundaries, and key assumptions are established; (2) Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) Analysis, which involves data collection and calculation procedures to quantify energy, water, and material inputs, as well as environmental releases; (3) Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), where the potential environmental impacts of the LCI results are evaluated; and (4) Interpretation, in which findings are assessed to ensure they align with the goal and scope, including an evaluation of uncertainties and data quality.

ISO 14044: This standard builds upon ISO 14040, offering more detailed requirements and guidelines for conducting an LCA. It elaborates on the methodologies for LCI and LCIA, emphasising the need for transparency, consistency, and comprehensiveness in data collection and impact assessment. It also provides specific rules for handling allocation, data quality analysis, and sensitivity checks. ISO 14044 is designed to ensure the credibility and comparability of LCA studies by standardising how assessments are performed and reported.

The ISO standards do not specify any specific metrics to be investigated. Instead, ISO 14044 gives guidance on the selection of impact categories and requires the selection to reflect a comprehensive set of environmental issues related to the product system being studied and in line with the goal and scope of the study.

2.2.1.2 Product Environmental Footprint (European Commission, 2021)

The Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) methodology, developed by the European Commission, is a comprehensive approach for assessing the environmental impacts of products throughout their life cycle. Designed to harmonise and improve the consistency of product environmental assessments, PEF aims to support more informed decisions by consumers, businesses, and policymakers.

PEF builds upon and aligns with the principles of the ISO 14040 standard, particularly in terms of LCA methodology. Like ISO 14040, PEF includes four key phases: (1) Goal and Scope Definition, (2) Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) Analysis, (3) Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), and (4) Interpretation. However, PEF provides additional specific guidance to enhance comparability across studies and to reduce methodological variability. Its alignment with ISO 14040 ensures that it integrates well with existing LCA frameworks while offering more specific guidance for environmental assessments in the European context.

A key feature of the PEF methodology is the inclusion of 16 environmental impact categories (metrics) to provide a more comprehensive assessment of environmental performance. These categories include climate change, resource use (both mineral and fossil), water use, acidification, eutrophication (terrestrial, marine, and freshwater), photochemical ozone formation, ozone depletion, ecotoxicity (terrestrial and aquatic), human toxicity, and ionising radiation. The PEF also requires a normalisation and weighting step to facilitate the comparison of environmental impacts across different products and categories.

2.2.1.3 ITU-T L.1400 standards (ITU-T L.1410 & L.1480) (ITU, 2014 and ITU, 2022)

The International Telecommunication Union ITU-T L.1400 series is a set of standards developed by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) focusing on the environmental sustainability of the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector. These standards provide methodologies and frameworks for assessing and mitigating the environmental impacts of ICT goods, networks, and services. For the purposes of the methodology for net impact assessment of functional electronics, the most relevant ITU-T standards include ITU-T L.1480, on which the EGDC method (EGDC, 2024; see section 3.2.1.4) is based, and ITU-T L.1410, which provides a methodological framework for the assessment of first order impacts of ICT solutions.

ITU standard ITU-T L.1480, titled “Enabling the Net Zero transition: Assessing how the use of information and communication technology solutions impact greenhouse gas emissions of other sectors”, provides a methodology for assessing the environmental impact of ICT products and services. The methodology specifically guides the assessment of ICT solutions by evaluating their net second order effects (*i.e.*, the secondary impacts after accounting for the initial emissions caused by the ICT solution) and higher order effects, such as rebound effects (see section 4.4 for more background). This standard builds on the guidance provided by the ITU-T L.1410 for the assessment of first order effects titled “Methodology for environmental impact assessment of information and communication technology goods, networks and services” which is based on the ISO LCA standards (ISO 14040 and ISO 14044) and provides additional ICT specific requirements, in addition to those of ISO LCA standards. The identification of the second and higher order effects is typically conducted by means of a consequence tree. In addition, the effect of contextual factors, such as policies, technological innovation and user behaviour need to be, at least, identified. Moreover, the methodology also distinguishes between effects associated with actual reductions of GHG emissions and lesser increases in GHG emissions, as well as between immediate and mid-term/long-term effects. **The aim of the assessment is the quantification of the difference between two scenarios, one with and one without the implementation of the ICT solution, and not to calculate an absolute impact.** This recommendation focuses on the assessment of GHG emissions

(metric). However, it could also be applied to identify other environmental effects, such as induced pollution, biodiversity preservation, and reduced use of raw materials or water resources.

ITU-T L.140 was developed jointly by ETSI TC EE (European Telecommunications Standards Institute Technical Committee Environmental Engineering) and ITU-T Study Group 5. It was published respectively by ITU as Recommendation ITU-T L.1410 and ETSI Standard ES 203 199, which are equivalent in technical content.

2.2.1.4 Net Carbon Impact Assessment Methodology for ICT Solutions (EGDC, 2024)

The Net Carbon Impact Assessment Methodology for ICT Solutions, developed by the EGDC, provides a structured approach to evaluate the carbon footprint and overall environmental impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions. The methodology is designed to assess whether ICT innovations contribute to reducing GHG emissions and whether they align with broader environmental sustainability goals.

Central to this methodology is the assessment of **net carbon impact**, which quantifies the difference between the GHG emissions generated by the ICT solution and the emissions avoided or reduced due to its deployment. This calculation includes direct emissions from the production, use, and end-of-life phases of the ICT solution, as well as indirect emissions related to energy consumption and supply chains. The quantification of the net carbon impact uses LCA as a basis. The goal is to ensure that the solution leads to a net reduction in emissions, contributing positively to climate goals.

In addition to GHG emissions, the methodology incorporates the "Do No Significant Harm" principle that is also included in the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities, ensuring that ICT solutions do not adversely affect other environmental aspects. This includes impacts on biodiversity, water and marine resources, pollution prevention, and the circular economy.

2.2.1.5 WBCSD Guidance on Avoided Emissions (2023)

The World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) provides guidance on the concept of avoided emissions, offering a framework for companies to assess and report the potential avoided GHG emissions of their products, services, or technologies. The guidance focuses on GHG emissions but indicates that the reasoning and principles can be replicated for other environmental indicators. Avoided emissions refer to the reductions in GHG emissions that occur outside a company's value chain, typically as a result of the use of its products or services, which enable lower emissions compared to conventional alternatives.

2.2.2 Methodologies for circularity assessment

2.2.2.1 ISO 59020 standard on Circularity Assessment (ISO, 2024)

The ISO 59020:2024 standard is part of the ISO 59000 family of standards which is designed to harmonise the understanding of the circular economy and to support its implementation and measurements. The standard provides a structured approach to measuring and assessing circularity performance and sustainability impacts based on standard indicators and complementary methods. The standard aims to standardise the process of data collection and calculation using circularity indicators, ensuring consistent and verifiable results.

The assessment process consists of three stages:

1. Boundary setting, where the system in focus is defined;
2. Circularity measurement and data acquisition, where circularity indicators are specified in relation to the data and information to be acquired, measured and calculated;
3. Circularity assessment and reporting, where the results of the circularity measurement are evaluated.

The metrics proposed by ISO 59020 consist of a core set of indicators, some of which are mandatory while others are optional. The core indicators can be complemented with additional ones. The mandatory core indicators are:

Resource inflow indicators:

- Average reused content of an inflow,
- Average recycled content of an inflow,
- Average renewable content of an inflow;

Resource outflow indicators:

- Percentage actual reused products and components derived from outflow,
- Percentage actual recycled material derived from outflow,
- Percentage actual recirculation of outflow in the biological cycle.

Optional indicators are indicators on energy, water and economic indicators (Annex 6.2).

Overall, the metrics proposed by ISO 59020 largely align with the circularity indicators outlined in the Material Circularity Indicator framework and the Circularity Transition Indicator framework, as described below.

2.2.2.2 Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019)

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation's Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) and related circularity indicators are designed to measure the circularity of products and companies, evaluating how well they align with circular economy principles. These indicators assess the extent to which materials are sourced, utilised, and managed to maintain their value within the economy for as long as possible. The scope of the MCI includes material sourcing, product design, manufacturing processes, usage, and end-of-life management.

The MCI emphasises the restoration of material flows at both the product and company levels and is guided by the following six principles:

- Sourcing biological materials from sustainable sources.
- Using feedstock from reused or recycled sources.
- Keeping products in use longer through reuse, redistribution, or increased durability.
- Reusing components or recycling materials after the product's lifecycle ends.
- Promoting more intensive use of products, such as through service, sharing, or performance models.
- Ensuring that biological materials remain uncontaminated and biologically accessible.

The MCI provides a single summary score, that is based on a combination of different indicators related to material sourcing, product design, and end-of-life management. It incorporates a utility factor, which considers the product's durability, reparability, and upgradeability. The methodology applies to both product-level and company-level assessments.

2.2.2.3 Circular Transition Indicators (CTI) (WBCSD, 2022)

The Circular Transition Indicators (CTI) framework developed by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) provides a methodology for assessing circular economy practices for businesses.

The CTI framework evaluates the circularity of operations, products, and supply chains, covering i.e. material use, product life cycles, and waste management. It provides a set of indicators that allows quantification of circularity performance, facilitating comparisons across different sectors and industries.

The framework is based on a self-assessment of material flows, focussing primarily on the circular and linear mass flows within company boundaries, combined with additional indicators on resource efficiency and efficacy, as well as the value added by circular business practices. The CTI framework also incorporates water, renewable energy, and business value into its scope. The framework does not evaluate the environmental and social impacts of the company's circular activities. CTI includes a methodology for measuring the impact of recycled sourcing on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reductions (GHG impact).

The CTI framework aligns with the Ellen MacArthur Foundation's circular economy principles:

- Design out waste and pollution;
- Keep products and materials in use;
- Regenerate natural systems.

2.3 Selection of methodologies and metrics

As introduced in section 3.2.1.4, the EGDC is an initiative of companies, supported by the European Commission and the European Parliament, based on the request of the EU Council, which aims to harness the enabling emission-reducing potential of digital solutions to all other sectors. The initiative envisions to bridge the methodological gap to clarify in a uniform and standardised manner the (positive) impacts of digitalisation on the environment and climate. The public tender CNECT/2021/OP/0005.¹⁰ was released by the European Commission in 2021 to conduct a Pilot Project. Published in 2024, the EGDC Net Carbon Impact Assessment methodology is an outcome of this Pilot Project. The **importance of this action for the EC is represented in the significant tender value (€ 1.2M)** that has been allocated for the development of this methodology¹¹. One objective of this Pilot Project is also to ensure its widespread adoption. With their aims to answer closely related methodological research needs, a **tailoring and instantiating of the EGDC methodology to the functional electronics field** (see section 1.2) is a logical starting point to build on most recent and available scientific work.

The **selection of the EGDC methodology is therefore deemed most suitable for the UNICORN project, meeting the specific requirements set out in section 2.1 effectively.** The EGDC methodology **excels** in its ability to account for **higher-order effects** of functional electronics, thereby capturing the benefits of their implementation. This is crucial for assessing the broader impacts and advantages of functional electronics. Additionally, the EGDC methodology is supported by a **comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for first and second-order effects, ensuring that the quantifiable environmental impacts are thoroughly analysed.**

With regard to LCA methodologies, ISO 14044 (2006) provides a standardised and widely recognised framework for LCA. It goes beyond just the carbon footprint, encompassing a broad range of environmental metrics. This multicriteria approach is essential to avoid burden shifting (for instance reducing climate change impact in one part of the system but increasing other impacts in other life cycle stages). The PEF, as an EU-developed methodology, uses the ISO standard as a basis, but provides additional specific guidance to enhance comparability across studies and to reduce methodological variability. Several disclosure requirements of different topical European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) included in Annex 1 of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) already recommend the use of the PEF methodology to calculate specific environmental impacts (e.g. pollution, water and marine resources-related impact) beyond GHG emissions.

While the EGDC methodology lists a wide range of possible LCA methodologies to quantify the environmental impact¹², **this framework for net impact assessment of functional electronics integration, proposes ISO 14044 with elements from PEF as the foundational basis for LCA.** Flexibility is granted to the assessor in the depth of implementing the PEF methodology as described in Chapter 3¹³. The PEF proposes a set of sixteen environmental

¹⁰ <https://etendering.ted.europa.eu/cft/cft-display.html?cftId=7822>

¹¹ Estimated tender value 1,200,000.00 EUR (<https://etendering.ted.europa.eu/cft/cft-display.html?cftId=7822>)

¹² The following LCA standards are mentioned: GHG Protocol, ITU-T L.1410, PAS 2050:2011, ISO 14067:2018, ISO 14044:2006

¹³ It is neither possible nor necessary to perform a fully compliant PEF assessment. Fully compliant assessments require the use of the EF database, which is only available free of charge for PEF studies following an official PEFCR. Additionally, other elements of PEF, such as the requirements for verification, the quantitative interpretation

metrics¹⁴. The metrics 'global warming potential' and **'fossil resource use' can be used to assess the total energy use and potential energy decarbonisation of functional electronics implementation.** Although not a direct measure of material circularity, 'fossil resource use' and 'resource use minerals and metals' provide insights into material circularity and optimised resource use. Adverse effects on human health are measured by the impact categories 'human toxicity (cancer and non-cancer)', 'particulate matter/respiratory inorganics', effect of 'ionising radiation' on human health and 'photochemical ozone formation'. Other impact categories are: 'acidification', which addresses the impacts of acidifying substances in the environment, 'eutrophication (terrestrial, freshwater and marine)' provides information on the effect of macro-nutrients in the environment, 'ecotoxicity' addresses the toxic impacts on an ecosystem, 'land use' deals with the occupation and conversion of land, 'water use' addresses the use of water taking into account its scarcity in the region where it is withdrawn. Finally 'ozone depletion' accounts for the degradation of stratospheric ozone. PEF also proposes a single score, which is a unitless number obtained after normalisation and weighting. Normalisation gives information on the magnitude of a category indicator result relative to the reference information (ISO 14044, 2006). In a weighting step indicator results are aggregated across impact categories using numerical factors based on value-choices. This single score offers a comprehensive metric that enables a straightforward comparison of the overall environmental performance of products and services (see section 4.2.4.1).

As shown in the requirements for the methodology (see section 2.1), the net impact of functional electronics integration should not only be considered in terms of energy and product decarbonisation but also with regards to their contribution to utilisation improvement, lifetime optimisation and material circularity. To ensure sustainability benefits of the integration, it is essential to prioritise circular strategies that also minimise environmental impacts. **Complementary assessment methods and metrics are therefore necessary to measure the circularity performance of functional electronics integration. Product-related indicators of ISO 59020 (2024) are considered the most relevant to be included in this assessment framework.**

This selection of methodologies and metrics for environmental impact and circularity assessment provides the necessary combination of indicators to evaluate the net impact of functional electronics integration along all transformation pathways.

The aim of the net impact assessment is not to compare different brands of solutions against each other, but to assess the impact of a functional electronics solution against a technological or methodical alternative that provides the same functionality.

of results and the quantitative data quality assessment are highly resource intensive. While these requirements are considered very useful for the comparison of the environmental performance of two or more products, they are deemed too demanding for the calculation of the net performance of functional electronics integration.

¹⁴ Within PEF, it is possible to develop Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules (PEFCR) for a certain sector. These rules allow for the selection of relevant metrics for that sector. Once the rules are established, PEF studies following the respective PEFCR may restrict the assessment to the relevant metrics for the sector. Relevant metrics are those that contribute up to 80% of the single score impact. A potential improvement to this methodology is to also make the assessment of the most relevant impact categories for the sector of functional electronics and report those metrics in this methodology.

Reading Guide

Chapters 4 and 5 of this document are directly related to the European Green Digital Coalition (EGDC) document titled: '[Net Carbon Impact Assessment Methodology for ICT Solutions](#)', (EGDC, 2024). These chapters follow the same structure as respectively Chapters 2 and 3 of the EGDC document and are complemented with assessment concepts defined by the PEF methodology. This document is recommended to be read in parallel with the EGDC methodology to provide optimal insight and guidance.

The aim of this document is to adapt the net impact assessment methodology for ICT solutions to meet the context of the UNICORN project and, by extension, to translate it to the functional electronics sector. Text that has been copied literally or with minor textual modifications from the EGDC document (EGDC, 2024) is in *italics*. This includes text where the terms 'net carbon impact assessment' and 'ICT solution' were replaced with 'net impact assessment' and 'functional electronics solution', respectively.

An application of the methodology on a UNICORN Use Case has been included in the boxes within the text to provide practical insights in how the methodology could be used.

3 Concepts

3.1 Functional electronics solution

As mentioned earlier (see section 1), the term 'Functional Electronics' was first introduced during the EU-funded project 5E (Federating European Electronics Ecosystems for Competitive Electronics Industries). Considering Nano-Electronics¹⁵, Electronics Smart Systems¹⁶ and Flexible, Organic & Printed Electronics¹⁷ as transversal enablers and differentiators of European digital transformation, one objective of the 5E project was to facilitate collaboration across the respective ecosystems.

As part of the 5E project, a joint vision for these three European electronics ecosystems was developed and the following definition of the concept was provided: "At the convergence of Unconventional Nanoelectronics, Flexible & Printed Electronics and Electronic Smart Systems, the term 'functional electronics' encompasses this ever-increasing capability to integrate key digital technologies with cognitive functions, shifting from purely physical integration to functional integration. Smarter (hybrid) electronic components and systems will become viable notably at high structural density on and in novel substrates (including, but not limited to, flexible, organic, printed) and structural systems (e.g. textiles, plastics, laminates, glass, steel)"¹⁸.

Here, we adapt the following definition of a functional electronics (FE) solution:

"A system that integrates advanced functionalities with physical components, extending beyond traditional electronics to deliver specific services to users; This system comprises all components essential for these advanced functionalities, including sensing, powering, signalling, actuating, monitoring, managing, processing, transmitting, and storing data. It also incorporates elements necessary to control or influence the system in its implementation."

3.2 Use case example

A "Use case example" serves as a practical illustration to demonstrate the application of the methodology principles described in this document. This example is employed to provide a

¹⁵ methodologies for integrating functions at high structural density on a single chip or device

¹⁶ concepts for combining cognitive functions with sensing, actuation, data communication and energy management

¹⁷ solutions enabling the production of flexible and large-area electronic components, opening up new functionalities and areas of application using a novel approach to manufacturing electronics

¹⁸<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5ceb6331&appId=PPGMS>

realistic context, thereby facilitating the understanding of theoretical concepts throughout their implementation. The use case illustrates the step-by-step application of the newly introduced concepts of the net impact methodology, showcasing how each principle and process can be applied to an actual situation. This approach aims to ensure the methodology's relevance and applicability to realistic FE solution scenarios.

Box 4.2 Use case example

The employed use case example encompasses two generations of a battery casing. Starting from a conventional battery casing with an indirect thermal management system. The ambition of the use case is to provide a lightweight, smart battery casing solution with integrated real-time thermal management and stress monitoring to maximise the battery performance, safety, lifetime and reusability that enables predictive maintenance and long-term sustainability.

3.3 Assessment concepts according to the EGDC method and the PEF method

In this section, we introduce the relevant assessment concepts derived from EGDC's Net Carbon Impact Assessment (NCIA) and complement them with principles from the ISO 14040 standard on LCA and the PEF method.

In section 4, we refine these assessment concepts specifically for functional electronics and demonstrate their application through a detailed use case. This approach ensures that the methodologies are tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of functional electronics, thereby enhancing the accuracy and relevance of the assessment.

3.3.1 Scenario

In environmental assessments, a scenario is a hypothetical construct that outlines a set of conditions or a sequence of events to evaluate the potential outcomes of different decisions or actions. Scenarios help in understanding the implications of implementing certain solutions, such as new technologies or policies, compared to a baseline or reference situation.

In the EGDC methodology, the assessment focuses on evaluating the overall change in emissions resulting from a specific solution. Scenarios enable for the comparison of carbon emissions of the baseline situation (reference scenario) with the scenario in which the new solution is implemented (solution scenario). They provide a comprehensive view of how different factors interact and contribute to overall carbon emissions, helping to identify direct and indirect effects.

3.3.1.1 Reference scenario

This assessment concept is applied in the EGDC methodology for NCIA. *The reference scenario represents the situation without implementing the solution. It comprises reference activities that form the end-to-end process, delivering the same service to the user as the solution, as defined by the functional unit (see section 3.3.3).*

3.3.1.2 Solution scenario

According to the EGDC methodology, *the solution scenario represents the situation where the solution is implemented. This solution may modify the reference activities (e.g., reducing resource use) or replace them with alternative activities (e.g., substituting travel). Additionally, some reference activities may remain unaffected.*

3.3.2 Solution description & assessment boundary (system boundaries)

The NCIA begins with a detailed description of the solution and its functionality. This includes identifying the key mechanisms by which the solution is expected to influence GHG emissions and specifying the sectors in which the solution is intended to be implemented. It also requires noting any limitations to the use of the solution, such as geographical, technical, or operational constraints. Additionally, the assessment outlines the solution boundary, describing all components comprising the solution.

While the NCIA focuses on the solution's functionality and its direct influence on GHG emissions, by adopting a dynamic approach that requires continuous updates, the system boundaries for most LCA's are defined in a more static manner from a product-level perspective. Specifically, the system boundary delineates which parts of the product life cycle and associated stages and processes are included in the analysis, excluding those omitted based on the cut-off rule. Any exclusions must be justified and documented. The system boundaries adhere to a general supply-chain logic, encompassing all stages from raw material acquisition, pre-processing, production, distribution, storage, and use, to end-of-life treatment. Additionally, co-products, by-products, and waste streams must be clearly identified.

These descriptions should be thoroughly completed at the start of the assessment. However, given that both NCIA and LCA are iterative processes, updates and additional information will likely be necessary as the assessment progresses and upon its completion.

3.3.3 Functional unit

In the EGDC methodology, *the functional unit is defined as the quantified performance of the system, serving as a reference unit to describe the GHG impacts of the solution. It establishes a common reference for measuring the quantity and quality of the service provided in both the reference and solution scenarios, allowing for a consistent comparison between the two.* This largely aligns with the functional unit concept applied in the PEF method in which this applies to a product system. The functional unit is used as a reference unit to qualitatively and quantitatively describe the function(s) and lifetime of the product in scope.

The functional unit in the PEF method is defined according to the following aspects:

- The function(s)/service(s) provided: "what";
- The extent of the function or service: "how much";
- The expected level of quality: "how well";
- The duration/lifetime of the product: "how long";

3.3.4 Implementation context

The reference and solution scenarios have to consider the context in which the solution is implemented as the context should be common to both scenarios. The implementation context will be described by a set of parameters that are constant between the reference and FE solution scenarios and by other contextual factors that can be described but do not have a defined parameter.

3.4 Components of a net carbon impact assessment

The net carbon impact of a solution is determined by comparing the full life cycle carbon emissions of the selected solution scenario with those of the reference scenario, both within the same boundary. The differences between these two scenarios are categorised into three distinct effects, which are defined in the following subsections:

- *First order effects*
- *Second order effects*
- *Higher order effects*

3.4.1 First order effects

According to the EGDC methodology, *first order effects are the life cycle impacts resulting directly from the components of the solution. These effects pertain to the direct impacts associated with the life cycle of the solution, which may include various components that require thorough assessment.*

3.4.2 Second order effects

Second order effects are the indirect impacts that arise from changes to the reference activities due to the deployment and use of the solution. These effects stem from the modification or replacement of the reference activities or from additional activities initiated by the solution's implementation. The resulting changes in GHG emissions are considered second order effects, which can be either positive (emission reductions) or negative (increased emissions due to additional or modified activities).

3.4.3 Higher order effects

Higher order effects are indirect impacts that arise as a consequence of second order effects, often following behavioural or structural changes such as shifts in consumption patterns, lifestyles, and value systems. These effects can be either positive or negative, and they encompass, but are not limited to, rebound effects. Higher order effects occur as causal chains of actions stemming from second order effects, with increasing uncertainty as these chains extend further. The distinction between second order and higher order effects can sometimes be unclear, as both types of effects are interlinked. The accurate categorisation of effects is less critical than ensuring all impacts are identified and assessed.

3.4.4 Rebound effects

Rebound effects, which are generally considered negative impacts, typically occur when increased efficiency leads to higher consumption. For example, a more efficient product is cheaper to operate, leading to increased usage. This improved efficiency can pertain to any resource, such as materials, time, cost, or space. Rebound effects can increase the impact of the solution by inducing additional demand for the solution (rebound usages) or generate additional GHG-emitting activities, both of which reduce the net carbon impact of the solution. Hence, considering only the first and second order effects of a solution can result in overly positive assessments of FE solutions as these benefits are not always fully realised by adapting to the new scenario created by the solution.

4 Assessing the net impact of the integration of functional electronics in a specific implementation context

In this section, the assessment steps defined in the EGDC methodology (EGDC, 2024) are applied to functional electronics and demonstrated through a detailed use case. The approach for ICT solutions has been tailored to the specific needs of UNICORN.

4.1 Assessment steps

The proposed assessment steps for calculating the net impact of functional electronics follow the same structure as those for calculating the net carbon impact calculation of an ICT solution with a few modifications. Within the scope of the UNICORN project, the 'Net carbon impact calculation' step should include the quantification of other environmental aspects, at least for first and second order effects. Resultantly, the scope of the assessment has been modified to 'Net impact calculation'. This modification renders the final step in the EGDC methodology 'Do No Significant Harm' redundant. For the review step, the wording has been changed from 'Critical review' to 'Review', to avoid confusion with the specific requirements outlined by the ISO 14040/44 for reviews of comparative LCA studies.

An LCA forms the basis for the 'Net Impact Calculation' step. The LCA should maintain the same boundaries and functional unit as used for the Net Impact Assessment. This is further detailed in section 4.4.

Also, the circularity assessment (CA) also provides input to the Net Impact Assessment. It helps identify of any potential trade-offs between material circularity and environmental impact reduction.

Figure 2: overview of the different steps of a net impact assessment (modified from EGDC's Net Carbon Impact Assessment steps), life cycle assessment (LCA) according to ISO 14040/44 standards and circularity assessment (CA) according to ISO 59020

4.2 Defining the Assessment (Goal and scope)

A net impact assessment quantifies the potential impacts generated by implementing a functional electronics (FE) solution compared to a reference scenario. Before starting the calculation, it is essential to fully define the FE solution and the assessment criteria, along with the context and purpose of the assessment. This step is crucial to establish the methodology's applicability, provide a basis for methodological decisions, and justify any assumptions used.

Within LCA studies, this step is referred to as the Goal & Scope. In the first phase of an LCA, the intended use, hereafter referred to as the goal, and the breadth and depth of the study, hereafter referred to as the scope, must be defined. The scope definition has to be consistent with the goal of the study. It is important to agree on the objective, the reference basis and the intended use of the study. Similarly, a circularity assessment according to ISO 59020 starts with the boundary setting.

4.2.1 Assessment objective (Goal)

Defining the assessment objective, or goal in common LCA terminology, is the first step of a net impact assessment and sets the overall context of the study. To establish the objective of the assessment, the assessor should consider the intended use of the results. By clearly determining the goal, also the aims, methods, results, and intended applications of the assessment are aligned, creating a shared vision to guide participants in the study.

The goal definition of a net impact assessment includes a clear and unambiguous description of:

- The reasons for carrying out the assessment;
- The intended use of its results;
- The audience(s) to which the results are intended to be communicated.

A net impact assessment also requires the definition of the implementation context of the functional electronics solution.

As part of the goal definition, it should be decided whether an ex-post or ex-ante assessment will be carried out, corresponding to whether the assessment aims to gather insights on actual effects or to identify potential effects.

LCA studies following the Product Environmental Footprint (European Commission, 2021) are ex-post assessments, measuring the impact that has occurred. They are not forward looking in nature. This methodology for net impact measurement of functional electronics implementation therefore proposes the use of ex-post evaluations.

Box 4.2.1 Assessment objective (use case example)

The goal of this study is to evaluate the environmental effects of different generations of (smart) battery casings with embedded temperature management and strain monitoring, developed in the UNICORN project.

The assessment is performed for several reasons and objectives, i.e.:

- gathering information about the first order environmental impacts and hotspots of printed electronics and alternative materials applied in battery casings;
- gathering information about the second and higher order effects associated with the implementation of the smart battery casing solution;
- gathering information on the circularity performance of the FE solution;
- identifying environmental improvement potential of the product system studied;
- gaining insight in the difference in environmental impact between the existing reference battery casing and the newly developed product with functional electronics integration;

The assessment will be performed from an ex-post perspective and a single implementation context will be considered, being the implementation of the battery casing in an EV.

The target audience of this study are the consortium members of the UNICORN project and the Commission Services. The obtained results will be used internally for product development purposes.

4.2.2 Solution description & boundary

This step and the following steps (sections 4.2.2 till 4.2.5 and section 4.3) are all part of the scope definition of an LCA study.

In this step, the solution to be assessed shall be clearly defined following the requirements of the EGDC (2024) methodology and a system boundary diagram shall be made.

4.2.2.1 Solution description

The FE solution to be assessed shall be clearly defined.

A FE solution is a system that integrates advanced functionalities with physical components, extending beyond traditional electronics to deliver specific services to users. Such a system comprises all components essential for these advanced functionalities, including sensing, powering, signalling, actuating, monitoring, managing, processing, transmitting, and storing data. It also incorporates elements necessary to control or influence the system in its implementation. The system boundary should encompass the entire FE solution with all components that are required for its functionality. *Since all components are likely to evolve over time, the description only needs to identify the components. Detailing different versions or technological changes is unnecessary unless it is relevant to the assessment.*

Box 4.2.2.1 Solution description (use case example)

The subject (solution) of this study is a smart battery casing with embedded strain sensors for stress monitoring and a real-time temperature management system. More specifically, this smart battery casing is composed of a casing which is made from recycled thermoplastic composite reinforced with flax fibres. In addition, the sensors encompass printed temperature sensors and printed strain gauges. These sensors are integrated in the developed casing using overmoulding. The FE solution will be applied in a mid-sized EV passenger car (automotive sector).

The functional electronics solution is expected to result in changes in emissions by improving the battery performance, improving the efficiency of the charging step, extending the battery lifetime, improving maintenance, improving reusability (including repurposing, refurbishing etc.).

For a more detailed description of the components we apply the system diagrams mentioned in the section below.

4.2.2.2 System boundary diagram

In LCA, the activities included in the assessment are typically presented graphically by means of a system boundary diagram. The system boundaries define which parts of the product life cycle and associated life cycle stages and processes belong to the analysed system (i.e., are required for carrying out its function as defined by the functional unit), excluding those processes omitted based on the cut-off rule. Any omissions should be clearly documented and justified in the light of the defined goal of the study.

A detailed visualisation of the system and its components shall be provided by means of system boundary diagram (or flow diagram) which is a schematic representation of the analysed system. It should clearly indicate the activities or processes included and excluded from the analysis.

The activity and/or process names in the system diagram and the report should be consistent.

4.2.3 Functional unit

The functional unit (FU) represents the quantified performance of a product system and serves as a reference unit. It establishes a common reference point for measuring both the quantity and quality of the service provided. The functional unit describes the function(s) and duration of the solution within the scope of the assessment, in this case both the solution and the reference scenario.

To appropriately define the functional unit, the approach from the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) shall be applied. The functional unit definition should answer the questions ‘what?’, ‘how much?’, ‘how well?’, and ‘for how long’.

- The function(s)/service(s) provided: “what”
- The extent of the function or service: “how much”

- The expected level of quality: “how well”
- The duration/lifetime of the product: “how long”

Integrating the aspects ‘how long’ and ‘how well’ into the definition of the functional unit implies that the effects of lifespan extension and efficiency improvements are included in the analysis and in the comparison of solutions.

Box 4.2.3 Functional unit (use case example)

The functional unit measures the performance of the system and provides a reference to which the input and output data will be normalised. In other words, the functional unit represents the quantified performance of a product system and serves as a reference unit and should answer following questions:

- The function(s)/service(s) provided: “what”
Encased battery delivering electrical energy measured in kWh.
- The extent of the function or service: “how much”
Encased EV battery delivering 1 kWh electrical energy.
- The expected level of quality: “how well”
Performance of the battery is at least 80% of original capacity
- The duration/lifetime of the product: “how long”
For the lifetime of the car, driven for 200 000 km

In this study, we applied the following functional unit:

1 kWh (kilowatt-hour) of the total output energy delivered over the EV service life by an encased battery (measured in kWh).

4.2.4 Assessment boundary

The assessment boundary determines which activities should be included in the impact assessment. It entails the definition of the environmental aspects and emissions to be included in the calculation, the circularity aspects to be included in the calculation, the time boundary of the assessment, its geographical boundary and the implementation context.

4.2.4.1 Environmental aspects

In the EGDC methodology (2024), the quantification of impacts is restricted to GHG emissions covered by the Kyoto Protocol, while other impacts are considered qualitatively as part of the “Do No Significant Harm” principle. The proposed methodology for net impact assessment of functional electronics in the scope of the UNICORN project requires the quantification of additional metrics beyond GHG emissions at least for first order and important second order effects to account for other environmental impacts and circularity.

Issues such as choice, modelling and evaluation of impact categories can introduce subjectivity throughout the assessment. To avoid this, the net environmental impact methodology uses the predefined impact categories and characterisation factors of the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method (European Commission, 2021) developed by the European Commission in the framework of the Product Environmental Footprint. These impact categories are considered for the LCA in order to assess the environmental impact of the different solutions.

Table 1 shows the impact categories of the EF method, Annex 1 contains some further explanation on what the different impact categories entail.

Table 1: Environmental impact categories defined by the EF3.1 method

Impact category	Indicator	Unit
Climate change ¹⁹	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq
Ozone depletion	Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq ²⁰
Human toxicity, cancer effects ²¹	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h
Human toxicity, non- cancer effects	Comparative Toxic Unit for humans (CTU _h)	CTU _h
Particulate matter	Human health effects associated with exposure to PM _{2.5} ²²	Disease incidences
Ionising radiation, human health	Human exposure efficiency relative to U ²³⁵	kBq U ²³⁵
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	Tropospheric ozone concentration increase	kg NMVOC eq ²³
Acidification	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol H ⁺ eq
Eutrophication, terrestrial	Accumulated Exceedance (AE)	mol N eq
Eutrophication, aquatic freshwater	Fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment (P)	kg P eq
Eutrophication, aquatic marine	Fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment (N)	kg N eq
Ecotoxicity freshwater ²¹	Comparative Toxic Unit for ecosystems (CTU _e)	CTU _e
Land use ²⁴	Soil quality index: - biotic production - erosion resistance - mechanical filtration - groundwater replenishment	Dimensionless ²⁵
Water use	User deprivation potential (deprivation- weighted water consumption)	kg world eq. deprived
Resource use, minerals and metals	Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)	kg Sb eq
Resource use, energy carriers	Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-fossil) ²⁶	MJ

As mentioned in section 2.3, PEF also proposes a single score, which is an aggregated measure that combines multiple environmental impact categories into a single, dimensionless value, expressed in Pt (points). This value is obtained through normalisation and weighting. Normalisation depicts the results of the different environmental impact categories into a common scale, enabling comparison and allowing aggregation by means of a weighting step.

¹⁹ The indicator “Climate Change, total” is a combination of three sub-indicators: Climate change –Change fossil; Climate change –Change biogenic; Climate change – land use and land use change. The sub-categories ‘Climate change –fossil’, ‘Climate change – biogenic’ and ‘Climate change - land use and land use change’ shall be reported separately, if they show a contribution of more than 5% each to the total score of climate change.

²⁰ CFC-11 = Trichlorofluoromethane, also called freon-11 or R-11, is a chlorofluorocarbon

²¹ excluding long-term emissions (occurring beyond 100 years)

²² Particulate Matter with a diameter of 2,5 µm or less

²³ NMVOC = Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds

²⁴ Refers to occupation and transformation

²⁵ Aggregated index of indicators: kg biotic production/ (m²*a), kg soil/ (m²*a), m³ water/ (m²*a) and m³ g.water/ (m²*a)

²⁶ Including uranium measured in MJ

The reference values, or normalisation factors, represent the total impact of a reference activity in a reference region for a certain impact category (e.g. climate change, eutrophication, etc.) in a reference year (Sala *et al.*, 2017). In the weighting step indicator results are aggregated across impact categories using numerical factors based on value-choices. The resulting weighted scores are summed to obtain a single impact score (Sala *et al.*, 2018). The EF method uses standardised weighting factors developed by the European Commission (European Commission, 2021).

The calculation of the single score, using the normalisation and weighting factors of the EF method is an integral part of a net environmental impact assessment of functional electronics.

4.2.4.2 Circularity performance

Similarly, for the circularity assessment, indicators were selected in accordance with the ISO 59020 standard, titled "Circular Economy - Measuring and Assessing Circularity Performance". A circularity indicator is a measure, either quantitative or qualitative, of an aspect of circularity. These indicators can be applied at any phase of a solution's life cycle, such as during simulation to evaluate circular designs, or throughout production, use, remanufacturing, repurposing, and recovery stages.

In line with ISO 59020, a list and description of core circularity indicators are provided for measuring and assessing circularity. Not all core circularity indicators are applicable at every system level or for all types of systems. When an indicator is not applicable, it can be marked as zero or "not applicable (N/A)" with a motivation. If relevant data are unavailable, they should be recorded as zero, accompanied with a statement explaining the data restrictions.

The circularity indicators are categorised to analyse material, water, and energy aspects separately, recognising that water and energy have unique characteristics essential for assessing circularity performance. Water, energy and economic indicators are described as optional core indicators in accordance with ISO 59020 (Annex 6.2). These indicators can supplement the mandatory core set of indicators if deemed relevant within the specific assessment context. Additionally, material criticality is considered a mandatory indicator within the context of this methodology as critical raw materials, often used in the manufacturing of electronics, play a significant role in determining the circularity, and overall sustainability, of these products. Many indicators offer percentage values (e.g., "average percent reused content of an inflow"), but absolute values with units should also be documented to ensure proper assessment and data aggregation.

Table 2 provides an overview of the circularity metrics selected within the context of this methodology.

Table 2: Circularity metrics

Indicator (unit)	Description
Average recycled content of an inflow (%)	$\frac{\text{mass recycled inflow} \times 100 \%}{\text{mass total inflow}}$ <p>A material qualifies as recycled content if it meets the ISO 14021:2016 (7.8.1.1) standards, including pre-consumer and post-consumer materials. It excludes materials reused within the same industrial process, such as rework, regrind, or scrap generated in a process and capable of being reclaimed within the same process that generated it.</p>
Average renewable content of an inflow (%)	$\frac{\text{mass renewable inflow} \times 100 \%}{\text{mass total inflow}}$ <p>Renewable material is biomass replenished at or above its depletion rate. Bio-based inflow is circular only if it is regeneratively sourced and sustainably managed, ensuring availability for future generations.</p>
Average reused content of an inflow (%)	$\frac{\text{mass reused inflow} \times 100 \%}{\text{mass total inflow}}$

	A resource inflow is reused content if it has already served a use. It can include materials and parts but does not include materials that have been processed through a recycling operation (recycled content).
Average virgin non-renewable content of an inflow (%)	$100\% - \text{average \% reused content} - \text{average \% recycled content} - \% \text{ virgin, renewable content}$
Circular inflow (%)	$\begin{aligned} & (\% \text{ circular inflow A} * \text{mass A}) \\ & + (\% \text{ circular inflow B} * \text{mass B}) \\ & + (\% \text{ circular inflow C} * \text{mass C}) \\ & \text{total mass of all inflow (A+B+C)} \end{aligned}$ <p>alternative calc. (top-down):</p> $\frac{[(\text{mass of renewable inflow} + \text{mass of non-virgin inflow})]}{\text{total mass of all inflow}} \times 100\%$ <p>Percentage of renewable content or percentage non-virgin content per inflow type. For the % circular inflow, both renewable and non-virgin materials are equally circular. If inflow is both, count it for only one category to avoid double counting.</p>
Actual reused content derived from outflow (%)	$\frac{\text{mass reused outflow} \times 100\%}{\text{mass total outflow}}$ <p>The “percent reused components and products from the outflow” indicator measures the fraction of outflow that is or will realistically be recovered for reuse in the production, maintenance, or repair of other resources or products.</p>
Actual recycled content derived from outflow (%)	$\frac{\text{mass recycled outflow} \times 100\%}{\text{mass total outflow}}$ <p>It calculates the average fraction of recycled material derived from resource outflow after recycling. If this concerns future recycling, estimates can be based on actual or industry average data from similar products in relevant regions, ensuring data does not overstate the recycled material expected from outflow.</p> <p>If traceable recyclability data are not available for a specific resource outflow, 0 % should be recorded.</p>
% actual recirculation of outflow in the biological cycle	$\frac{\text{mass biological recirculation outflow} \times 100\%}{\text{mass total outflow}}$ <p>The ‘percent actual recirculation of outflow in the biological cycle’ indicator measures the fraction of outflow recirculated at end of life for safe return to the biosphere through biodegradation, meeting recirculation conditions for e.g. composting or anaerobic digestion. It describes materials fully decomposed by microorganisms into organic molecules for use by living systems.</p>
Critical inflow (%)	$\frac{\text{m of inflow defined as critical} \times 100\%}{\text{total mass of linear inflow}}$ <p>This indicator shows the percentage of inflow at risk by distinguishing between critical and non-critical raw materials according to the assessment method of the European Commission (European Commission, 2023) (Annex 6.3). This indicator is taken from the CTI framework as material criticality is deemed relevant due to the significant role of critical raw materials in electronics (WBCSD, 2022).</p>

To achieve a balanced measurement, the mandatory core circularity indicators must be included when assessing resource inflows and outflows. When applicable, circularity indicators related to energy, water, and economics should also be included in the assessment.

4.2.4.3 Temporal boundary of the assessment

A time boundary should be defined for the assessment. In general, the full lifetime of the application in which the functional electronics are used shall be considered.

Ex-post assessments evaluate the actual impact of implemented solutions and are used for public reporting of net impacts. They can cover the full lifetime of the solution up to the assessment date (i.e. the cumulative impact over the lifetime) or a shorter period (e.g. annual reporting). The inventory data should always be linked to the functional unit.

Ex-ante assessments estimate potential future impacts based on assumptions about future conditions and performance. They are useful for strategic decision-making and gaining insights into potential activities but should not be used for public reporting of net environmental impacts due to significant uncertainties. They require assumptions on e.g. future grid electricity mixes.

Net impact assessment following this methodology should be ex-post assessments, which is similar to perspective taken in the Product Environmental Footprint methodology.

4.2.4.4 Geographical boundary of the assessment

Similarly, the geographic boundary of the assessment should be defined, which should be done in relation to the implementation of the solution. This can be a region our country where the activities in the reference and solution scenario take place. The geographical boundary defines the region where the activities occur but does not exclude activities upstream of the supply chain from the calculation if they happen outside this boundary. Resources sourced from outside the boundary must still be included in the assessment. Consistent application of the geographical boundary is essential throughout the assessment.

4.2.4.5 Implementation context

The implementation context is the system in which the solution is applied. It must be clearly defined to ensure that all necessary parameters in both the reference and solution scenarios remain constant throughout the assessment, guaranteeing comparability between the scenarios. The system description should be as detailed as possible, and any characteristic significantly affecting the assessment results should be treated as a parameter within the assessment.

Box 4.2.4. Temporal and geographic boundary, implementation context (use case example)

For the evaluation of the smart battery casing, an ex-post assessment will be conducted within the geographical boundary of EU27. The FE solution will be applied in a mid-sized EV passenger car that is driven for 200 000 km under EU traffic conditions and infrastructure.

4.2.5 Reference scenario definition

The accuracy and credibility of a net impact assessment are directly influenced by the determination of the reference scenario. Therefore, in this methodology as well, it is crucial for the assessor to accurately identify and justify the selection of the reference scenario.

The reference scenario should be determined as the most likely alternative scenario in the event the solution is not or was not implemented. It must have equivalent or less functionality than the FE solution, be relevant to the given implementation context, and be relevant to the time during which the FE solution is being assessed. The most likely scenario is identified as either the continued use of the known system previously in place or the use of the average alternative solution or method that users would select to achieve the same service. If necessary, the reference scenario should include multiple scenarios to accurately represent the most likely alternative scenario. The assessor must describe how the function is fulfilled in the reference scenario.

Box 4.2.5 Definition of reference scenario (use case example)

The reference scenario for the FE solution encompasses a conventional (aluminium) battery casing without a real-time thermal management system (printed temperature sensors and dielectric fluid cooling and heating system) and without real-time stress monitoring functionalities (printed strain gauge). More specifically, the conventional battery management system encompasses an aluminium cooling plate with a glued thermal interface with the cells.

4.3 Identifying effects

Once the assessment is delineated, the next step involves identifying all effects stemming from the implementation of the FE solution. This can be accomplished by following the 5-step process outlined below as mentioned in the EGDC methodology:

- 1. Identify activities and emission sources for both the reference and FE solution scenarios.*
- 2. Identify potential effects associated with implementing the solution.*
- 3. Map these effects using a consequence tree.*
- 4. Identify first-order effects.*
- 5. Identify second and higher-order effects.*

The subsequent sections provide more detailed information on each step of the process.

4.3.1 Identifying reference and solution scenario activities and emission sources

Within the context of this methodology, the activities and associated sources of potential emissions under the reference and FE solution scenarios are assessed. The priority here is on identifying activities rather than their associated sources of potential emissions. While the EGDC methodology requires the identification of both activities and associated sources of potential GHG emissions, broadening the scope to a wider range of environmental impact categories complicates this exercise. The identification of sources of emissions should, in a net impact assessment of FE, be part of the interpretation of the results.

All activities required to fulfil the defined function provided under the specified assessment boundary under both the reference and FE solution scenario should be listed (see Table 3).

Functional electronics solutions that optimise reference activities will share the same activities between the reference and solution scenarios, though these activities are modified in the FE solution scenario. In contrast, solutions that replace reference activities will lead to different activities in the reference scenario compared to the solution scenario. In cases of partial substitution, the solution scenario must incorporate the ongoing activities from the reference scenario, albeit in a modified form.

Box 4.3.1 Activities under the reference and FE solution scenarios (use case example)

Table 3: Activities under the reference and FE solution scenarios

Reference scenario	FE solution scenario
Production of aluminium battery casing	Production of composite battery casing
Production of BMS	Production of BMS
	Production printed temperature sensors and strain gauge
	Production of real-time thermal management system
Production of battery cells	Production of battery cells
Integration of BMS in casing	Integration of BMS and additional sensors and strain gauge in casing
Assembly of battery cells in casing	Assembly of battery cells in casing
Packaging	Packaging
Distribution	Distribution
Assembly in car	Assembly in car
Use in car	Use in car
Monitoring of voltage, current and temperature	Monitoring of voltage, current, temperature and strain
	Real-time management of temperature

4.3.2 Mapping effects in a consequence tree

A consequence tree offers an analytical method to identify secondary and higher-order effects. By means of a consequence tree all first, second and higher order effects can be mapped and visualised. It uses the sequence of effects as a foundation to obtain an overview of the outcomes associated with the implementation and to uncover additional impacts. Hence, for each identified effect, a causal chain of subsequent effects should be created.

Making the distinction between a second order or higher order effect can pose difficulties, nevertheless, the aim is to ensure that the effect is identified and included in the assessment regardless of whether it is a second or higher order effect.

Guidance on identifying and categorising first, second and higher order effects is provided in the EGDC methodology sections 3.3.4 and 3.3.5.

The EGDC methodology requires the mapping of GHG impact on the consequence tree. While this is relevant within the EGDC framework, where only GHG emissions are considered, it will be impossible to comprehensively capture all environmental effects in a consequence tree. Therefore, this can be omitted in the construction of the consequence tree following the proposed methodology for net impact assessment of FE solutions.

Box 4.3.2 Consequence tree (use case example)

Figure 4: Consequence tree for use case example depicting the first order, second order and higher order effects of a smart battery casing solution. SOH: state of health; SOC: state of charge; SOT: state of temperature.

4.4 Calculating effects

This part of the assessment involves the quantification of the environmental and circularity impacts of the FE solution. Where the EGDC methodology provides the option to perform a 'light LCA', this methodology requires that the quantifications are based on a full LCA, at least for the first order effects and for the most important and quantifiable second order effects. The LCA should be conducted in accordance with ISO 14044 (2006) and should follow the additional specifications (e.g. impact categories) provided in this document. The Product Environmental Footprint (European Commission, 2021) can be used as an additional source of information for the LCA. For the circularity assessment, ISO 59020 (2024) can be used as a basis.

4.4.1 Identify relevant effects (Estimating the relative magnitude of effects)

This step involves identifying relevant effects from the consequence tree that are considered to create a relevant change in impact.

For first order effects, the cut-off rules of the Product Environmental Footprint guidelines (European Commission, 2021) are applicable. This means that cut-offs shall be avoided as far as possible, in any case, processes and elementary flows may be excluded up to 3.0% (cumulatively) based on material and energy flows and the level of environmental significance (single overall score).

For some of the mapped second and higher order effects, it may be evident that they do not carry a significant environmental burden or that there are no substantial differences expected between the reference situation and the situation with the functional electronics implemented. Qualitative assessments are recommended for this step. The output should be a consequence tree in which effects deemed irrelevant and therefore not further investigated are marked. A justification for the exclusion of anticipated effects from the assessment should be given.

4.4.2 Data Collection

4.4.2.1 Identifying activities and emission factors (LCI data sources)

For the calculation of first order effects and quantifiable second order effects, data collection shall be conducted in accordance with ISO 14044 (2006) standard. The input data shall be related to the functional unit. Validation of data involves establishing mass and energy balances.

Primary data (or company-specific data) shall be collected for the manufacturing processes of the functional electronics.

Secondary data can be sourced from LCA databases, such as ecoinvent (Wernet et al., 2016).

4.4.2.2 Data quality and availability assessment

ISO, PEF and EGDC provide guidance on data quality assessment. Data quality assessment for net impact calculations of functional electronics should follow the guidance provided in the EGDC (2024) methodology. The depth of the data quality assessment can be adjusted according to the purpose of the study.

4.4.3 First order effects

The impact of all first order effects shall be calculated for each implementation context within the boundary conditions except for those excluded by the cut-off criteria.

The cut-off rules outlined in the PEF guidelines (European Commission, 2021) are applicable. This means that cut-offs shall be avoided as much as possible, however, processes and elementary flows may be excluded up to 3.0% (cumulatively) based on material and energy flows and the level of environmental significance (calculated using the overall single score).

Similar to EGDC methodology, first order effects shall be calculated for all life cycle phases, including use phase and end-of-life phase. The impact of first order effects shall be calculated in relation to the functional unit. Additionally, a conservative approach shall be applied.

A full LCA is required for all components of the solution; light LCAs are not permitted. ISO 14044 (2006) is the primary standard to be followed, supplemented where relevant by elements of the PEF method (European Commission, 2021).

4.4.4 Second order effects

The impact of all identified second order effects (positive and negative changes to the reference scenario) shall be calculated for the same implementation context except for those excluded by the cut-off criteria.

Also for second order effects, the cut-off rules of the Product Environmental Footprint guidelines (European Commission, 2021) are applicable. This means that cut-offs shall be avoided as far as possible, in any case, processes and elementary flows may be excluded up to 3.0% (cumulatively) based on material and energy flows and the level of environmental significance (single overall score).

Similar to EGDC methodology, second order effects shall be calculated from a life cycle perspective. The impact of second order effects shall be calculated in relation to the functional unit. Additionally, a conservative approach shall be applied.

The EGDC methodology outlines different calculation approaches regarding data availability for second order effects for both the reference and solution situation. It provides guidance to the assessor, but as noted, in practice calculations may not precisely match the different approaches.

4.4.5 Higher order effects

The requirements from the EGDC methodology are applicable.

For the assessment of higher order effects, the relative magnitude of all impacts should be evaluated. This includes a quantitative estimation where feasible or a qualitative assessment where a precise estimation is not possible. The estimation should consider the effect's magnitude relative to the total net impact. Understanding the relative magnitude helps determine necessary data requirements and justifies the exclusion of effects based on cut-off criteria, enabling organisations to focus resources on the most significant elements of the analysis.

The output should document the estimated relative magnitude of all identified effects and key methodological and data decisions. The relative magnitude may need to be updated iteratively as initial estimations are refined with primary data. Once the net impact assessment is completed, the estimation should be repeated with final emissions data to validate any cut-offs and data choices.

If specific calculations are limited by data availability, a qualitative assessment can be used. This should consider the potential order of magnitude of an impact relative to other identified effects. The significance of each effect (e.g., low, medium, or high) should be estimated and explained.

4.5 Net impact calculation

4.5.1 Net environmental impact calculation

The total net environmental impact of the solution should be calculated, encompassing all quantified first, second, and higher-order effects within the time boundary of the assessment. Any significant changes to the impacts of these effects during the assessment period must also be included in the evaluation.

After calculating the impacts from first, second, and higher-order effects, the net impact of the solution can be determined per environmental impact category. The assessor must ensure that

all relevant effects within the assessment boundary are included. The net calculation aggregates, per impact category, the impacts of all effects based on the selected functional unit (FU). Therefore, the net impact of environmental aspect X for the functional unit is calculated as:

$$Net\ Impact_{FU, X} = Reference\ scenario\ X - [\Sigma 1st\ Order\ Effects\ X + \Sigma 2nd\ Order\ Effects\ X + \Sigma Higher\ Order\ Effects\ X]$$

Hence, the net impact is the sum of all the effects, in which emissions are positive values and reductions in emissions are negative. Higher order effects might only be assessed qualitatively.

A positive result indicates that the solution scenario has led to a reduction in environmental impact compared to the reference scenario. A negative result shows that the implementation of the functional electronics provides no overall environmental benefit.

Figure 5 provides an illustrative example in the format of a Waterfall graph, for the net impact calculation for the impact category climate change, being the net carbon impact. A similar figure can be made for other environmental effects and for the single score (Box 5.5).

Figure 5: Illustrative example net carbon impact

Box 4.5 Net environmental impact calculation (use case example)

Since this use case example serves as merely an illustrative case for the exemplification of the described method, using impact numbers from the use cases²⁷ we focus on calculating the single score impact, which is the sum of the normalised and weighted results of all environmental impact categories. Furthermore, only a subset of first order, second order and higher order effects has been considered as an illustration. More specifically, for the reference scenarios following impacts are considered:

- Battery production

²⁷ For the impact of the reference and solution scenario, real impact numbers are applied based on UC1

- Aluminium battery casing

For the solution scenario following impacts are considered:

- Battery production
- Composite battery casing
- Production of printed temperature sensors and strain gauge

As the production processes of the battery and conventional sensors are identical in both scenarios, the assessment focuses solely on the impacts of the aluminium casing in the reference scenario. The solution scenario considers the impacts associated with the composite casing, along with the integrated printed temperature sensors, strain gauge, and management system.

Functional unit

1 kWh (kilowatt-hour) of the total output energy delivered over the life of an encased battery (measured in kWh).

Calculation assumptions

- Reference Scenario: A battery delivers 30 000 kWh over its serviceable life in an EV before its capacity is reduced to 80% (Pesaran, A. et al., 2023).
- Solution Scenario: A battery encased in the smart battery casing delivers 33 000 kWh over its serviceable life before its capacity is reduced to 80% (Pesaran, A. et al., 2023).
- Due to the use of a direct thermal management system (TMS) in the solution scenario, which replaces the conventional indirect TMS based on cold plates and coolant, a conservative battery lifetime improvement of 10% is assumed based on expert judgement and literature (Larrañaga-Ezeiza, M et al., 2025).

Additional considerations

Battery reuse:

- In the solution scenario, it is assumed that through strain monitoring and predictive maintenance, the battery can be repurposed for use in a stationary application, whereas in the reference scenario the battery is not reusable. The environmental impact of a stationary battery with a capacity of 20 kWh, including its battery management system (BMS) and cooling system, is estimated at 1,447 kg CO₂-eq (climate change) or 448 mPt (single score impact).
- The production of a functionally equivalent stationary battery can be avoided in the solution scenario.

Impact calculation

Impacts are expressed in relation to the FU (amount of kWh delivered by the battery).

Table 4 depicts the impacts associated with the different scenarios.

Table 4: Impact calculation

Scenario	Impact	Impact relative to FU
Reference scenario	Baseline impact: 1 791 mPt	$\frac{1\,791\text{ mPt}}{30\,000\text{ kWh}} = 59,7\ \mu\text{Pt}$
Solution scenario	Baseline impact: 1 787 mPt	$\frac{1\,787\text{ mPt}}{33\,000\text{ kWh}} = 54,1\ \mu\text{Pt}$
Solution scenario (2 nd order effect – life extension)	0,909 * 1787 mPt = 1624 mPt 1791 mPt – 1624 mPt = 167 mPt (avoided)	0,909 * 54,1 μPt = 49 μPt 59,7 μPt – 49 μPt = 10,7 μPt (avoided)
Solution scenario (higher order effect)	447,74 mPt (avoided)	14 μPt (avoided)

NEI = 1 791 mPt - [1 787 mPt – 167 mPt – 448 mPt] = 619 mPt

NEI per FU = 59 μPt – [54 μPt – 11 μPt – 14 μPt] = 30 μPt

Figure 6: Calculations for the net environmental impact of the use case example

4.5.2 Circularity assessment

The circularity metrics (see Table 2) shall be calculated for the reference scenario and the solution scenario. Circularity metrics are often challenging to calculate across the entire value chain and to account for higher-order effects. Depending on the study's goal, their application may be limited to the product level, without considering the full system or broader systemic impacts.

4.6 Uncertainty and Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analysis should be carried out for all key parameters as part of the net impact assessment. The sensitivity analyses of all key inputs should be combined to create a lower and higher uncertainty range for each effect included in the net impact assessment, as well as giving an overall uncertainty range for the impact assessment of the FE solution.

Uncertainty can be approached by using sensitivity assessments, uncertainty ranges can be made using the single score outcome of the assessment. This is sufficient to reach the goal of the UNICORN project. Depending on the goal and scope of the net impact assessment, other approaches towards uncertainty and sensitivity might be more appropriate. Further guidance is provided in the EGDC methodology.

4.7 Critical Review

At least an internal review of the study is necessary. This methodology does not aim to provide further guidance on the review process. The type of review required depends on the goal of the study. The net impact assessment studies conducted as part of the UNICORN project will undergo an internal review.

4.8 Recalculation

This methodology does not specify any requirements regarding recalculations. The EGDC methodology (2024) requires an annual review before continuing to use the assessment results. Depending on the identified changes, recalculations of the study in whole or in part may be required.

4.9 Consideration of other environmental impacts

A net impact assessment of functional electronics solutions following this methodology requires the calculation and reporting of environmental impacts listed in Table 1 and circularity indicators in Table 2. The assessment thus covers a broad range of environmental aspects. However, users of this methodology are free to report supplementary environmental impacts as additional information.

5 References

- EGDC. 2024. *Net Carbon Impact Assessment Methodology for ICT Solutions*. The European Green Digital Coalition. Funded by the European Union. Lead Authors: Veronika Thieme and Felix Prettejohn. <https://www.greendigitalcoalition.eu/net-carbon-impact-assessment-methodology-for-ict-solutions/>.
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. 2019. *Circularity Indicators: an Approach to Measuring Circularity*. <http://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circularity-indicators/>
- European Commission. 2021. "Commission Recommendation of 16.12.2021 on the Use of the Environmental Methods to Measure and Communicate the Life Cycle Environmental Performance of Products and Organisations." European Commission. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/recommendation-use-environmental-footprint-methods_en.
- European Commission. 2023. *Study on the Critical Raw Material for the EU 2023 – Final Report*. European Commission. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/57318397-fdd4-11ed-a05c-01aa75ed71a1>
- ISO. 2006a. "International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland, ISO 14040:2006: Environmental Management – Life Cycle Assessment – Principles and Framework."
- . 2006b. "International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland, ISO 14044:2006: Environmental Management – Life Cycle Assessment – Requirements and Guidelines."
- . 2024. "International Organisation for Standardisation, Switzerland, ISO 59020:2024: Circular Economy - Measuring and Assessing Circularity Performance."
- ITU-T. 2014. "Recommendation of ITO-T L.1410, Methodology for Environmental Life Cycle Assessments of Information and Communication Technology Goods, Networks and Services. Series L: Construction, Installation and Protection of Cables and Other Elements of Outside Plant. Telecommunication Standardisation Sector of ITU." <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-L.1410-201412-I>.
- . 2022. "Recommendation of ITO-T L.1480, Enabling the Net Zero Transition: Assessing How the Use of Information and Communication Technology Solutions Impact Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Other Sectors. Series L: Environment and ICTs, Climate Change, e-Waste, Energy Efficiency: Construction, Installation and Protection of Cables and Other Elements of Outside Plant. International Telecommunication Union, Standardisation Sector." <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-L.1480-202212-I>.
- Larrañaga-Ezeiza M., Vertiz G., Galarza I., Grande H.J., Arroiabe P.F., Berasategi J., Martinez-Agirre M. 2025. *Partial direct liquid cooling approach for battery modules based on pouch type cells: A novel solution for electromobility applications*. Journal of Energy Storage, volume 121, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2025.116566>
- Pesaran A., Roman L., Kincaide J., *Electric Vehicle Lithium-Ion Battery Life Cycle Management*, Golden, CO: National Renewable Energy Laboratory. NREL/TP-5700-84520 <https://docs.nrel.gov/docs/fy23osti/84520.pdf>
- Sala S., Cerutti A.K., Pant R., *Development of a weighting approach for the Environmental Footprint*, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-68042-7, EUR 28562, doi:10.2760/945290
- Sala S., Crenna E., Secchi M., Pant, R., *Global normalisation factors for the Environmental Footprint and Life Cycle Assessment*, EUR (28984), Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2017, ISBN 978-92-79-77213-9, doi:10.2760/88930, JRC109878
- UNEP-SETAC. 2011. "Global Guidance Principles for Life Cycle Assessment Databases." <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/12/2011%20-%20Global%20Guidance%20Principles.pdf>.
- Weidema, Bo. 2003. "Market Information in Life Cycle Assessment. Environmental Project No. 863 2003." Danish Environmental Protection Agency.

- Wernet, Gregor, Christian Bauer, Bernhard Steubing, Jürgen Reinhard, Emilia Moreno-Ruiz, and Bo Weidema. 2016. "The Ecoinvent Database Version 3 (Part I): Overview and Methodology." *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 21 (9): 1218–30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>.
- World Business Council for Sustainable Development. 2022. *Circular Transition Indicators v3.0: Metrics for Business by Business*. <https://www.wbcSD.org/resources/circular-transition-indicators-v3-0/>
- World Business Council for Sustainable Development. 2023. *Guidance on Avoided Emissions: Helping Business Drive Innovations and Scale Solutions toward Net Zero*. https://www.wbcSD.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Climate-Avoided-Emissions-guidance_WBCSD.pdf.

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex 1: The environmental impact categories of the Product Environmental Footprint methodology

Source: European Commission (2021)

Climate Change/Global Warming Potential (kg CO₂ equivalent)

Capacity of a greenhouse gas to influence radiative forcing, expressed in terms of a reference substance (for example, CO₂-equivalent units) and specified time horizon (e.g. GWP 20, GWP 100, GWP 500, for 20, 100, and 500 years respectively). It relates to the capacity to influence changes in the global average surface-air temperature and subsequent change in various climate parameters and their effects, such as storm frequency and intensity, rainfall intensity and frequency of flooding, etc.

Ozone Depletion (kg CFC-11 equivalent)

EF impact category that accounts for the degradation of stratospheric ozone due to emissions of ozone-depleting substances, for example long-lived chlorine and bromine containing gases (e.g. CFCs, HCFCs, Halons)

Human toxicity: cancer (CTUh)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human beings caused by the intake of toxic substances through inhalation of air, food/water ingestion, penetration through the skin insofar as they are related to cancer.

Human toxicity: non-cancer (CTUh)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human beings caused by the intake of toxic substances through inhalation of air, food/water ingestion, penetration through the skin insofar as they are related to non-cancer effects that are not caused by particulate matter/respiratory inorganics or ionising radiation.

Particulate Matter/Respiratory Inorganics (disease incidence)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human health caused by emissions of Particulate Matter (PM) and its precursors (NO_x, SO_x, NH₃)

Ionising Radiation, human health (kBq U235 equivalent)

EF impact category that accounts for the adverse health effects on human health caused by radioactive releases.

Photochemical Ozone Formation (kg NMVOC equivalent)

EF impact category that accounts for the formation of ozone at the ground level of the troposphere caused by photochemical oxidation of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) and carbon monoxide (CO) in the presence of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and sunlight. High concentrations of ground-level tropospheric ozone damage vegetation, human respiratory tracts and manmade materials through reaction with organic materials.

Acidification (mol H⁺ equivalent)

EF impact category that addresses impacts due to acidifying substances in the environment. Emissions of NO_x, NH₃ and SO_x lead to releases of hydrogen ions (H⁺) when the gases are mineralised. The protons contribute to the acidification of soils and water when they are released in areas where the buffering capacity is low, resulting in forest decline and lake acidification.

Eutrophication terrestrial (mol N eq), freshwater (kg P equivalent) and marine (kg N equivalent)

Nutrients (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus) from sewage outfalls and fertilised farmland accelerate the growth of algae and other vegetation in water. The degradation of organic material consumes oxygen resulting in oxygen deficiency and, in some cases, fish death. Eutrophication translates the quantity of substances emitted into a common measure expressed as the oxygen required for the degradation of dead biomass.

To assess the impacts due to eutrophication, three EF impact categories are used: eutrophication, terrestrial; eutrophication, freshwater; eutrophication, marine.

Ecotoxicity (CTUe)

Environmental footprint impact category that addresses the toxic impacts on an ecosystem, which damage individual species and change the structure and function of the ecosystem. Ecotoxicity is a result of a variety of different toxicological mechanisms caused by the release of substances with a direct effect on the health of the ecosystem.

Land use (pt)

EF impact category related to use (occupation) and conversion (transformation) of land area by activities such as agriculture, roads, housing, mining, etc. Land occupation considers the effects of the land use, the amount of area involved and the duration of its occupation (changes in quality multiplied by area and duration). Land transformation considers the extent of changes in land properties and the area affected (changes in quality multiplied by the area).

Water use (m³ world equivalent)

No definition provided in reference European Commission (2013)

Impact category that addresses use of water.

Resource use, minerals and metals (kg Sb equivalent)

EF impact category that addresses use of natural resources, either renewable or non-renewable, biotic or abiotic.

Resource use, fossils (MJ)

EF impact category that addresses use of natural resources, either renewable or non-renewable, biotic or abiotic.

6.2 Annex 2: Optional indicators

Indicator (unit)	Description
Average lifetime (relative to industrial average)	$\frac{\text{t life of product or material}}{\text{t average life}}$ <p>The “average lifetime of product or material relative to industry average” indicator measures how well a resource outflow retains its value over time compared to the industry average. This represents the slowing of resource flow and is relevant when the system produces products or materials for user functions.</p>
Average % consumed renewable E	$\frac{\text{energy inflow renew.} - \text{energy outflow renew.}}{\text{total E inflow} - \text{total E outflow}} \times 100 \%$ <p>The “average percent of energy consumed that is renewable” measures the fraction of total energy consumption that is renewable. This indicator accounts for both energy inflows and outflows, including energy used for manufacturing, by-products, or resource management. It also considers non-renewable inputs for capturing, transmitting, and converting renewable energy to electricity, which should be monitored to assess circularity.</p>
Water withdrawal from circular sources (%)	$\frac{\text{total quantity of circular water withdrawal}}{\text{total quantity of water withdrawal}} \times 100 \%$ <p>This indicator shows the percentage of annual water demand met by circular sources, which recirculate water within a process or the hydrologic cycle. Circular water sources must meet the following criteria:</p> <p>a) Prior use or natural renewability: Water from non-virgin sources, such as reused or recycled water, renewable freshwater sources (surface, ground, rainwater), non-freshwater sources (sea or brackish water), or water in raw materials. After use, it is returned to the local watershed after treatment.</p> <p>b) Water management plan: A plan to minimise impacts on local environments</p>
Water discharged in accordance with quality requirements (%)	$\frac{\text{volume of circular water discharges}}{\text{volume of water inflow from all sources}} \times 100 \%$ <p>This indicator measures the percentage of water consumed in processes and operations that is either reused by another organisation or returned to the water source at the same or better quality, as per environmental authority guidelines. Key water quality parameters include BOD, pH, and temperature. ISO 22447 and ISO 14046 provide relevant water quality standards.</p> <p>Losses like effluents, spills, or evaporation not returned to the local source are non-circular outflows. The total water withdrawn should equal the sum of non-circular outflows, water in products, and circular discharges. Circular water discharges must meet quality standards for environmental, social, agricultural, or industrial uses.</p>
Water reuse or recirculation (n/a)	$\frac{\text{volume of total water use per year}}{\text{volume of total water withdrawn}}$ <p>The “ratio of on-site water reuse or recirculation” indicator measures water circularity within a facility over a reporting period. It compares total water use to the amount withdrawn from all sources. This ratio exceeds 1.0 when water is reused or recirculated, indicating the facility uses more water than it withdraws. An external source is one from a local supply and not provided by internal processes or operations.</p>
Material productivity	$\frac{\text{revenue generated}}{\text{total mass of all linear resource inflows}}$ <p>The material productivity (MP) indicator, measures the ratio of an organisation’s revenue to its total linear (non-circular) resource inflows.</p>

	This indicator reflects how effectively a company generates income while reducing its reliance on linear resources.
Resource intensity index	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>resource consumption</u> economic value rate</p> <p>The resource intensity index (RII), also known as the decoupling index, measures the ratio of the change in resource consumption to the change in GDP over time, providing a quantitative measure of economic growth versus resource use. While typically used at the regional level, it can be adapted for products or organisations by using metrics like revenue.</p>
Substances of concern in material outflow	The presence of substances of concern in material outflow can specify as additional resource outflow indicator. Safe material choices, essential for circularity, become measurable in the outflow when systems thinking is applied at the design stage. Avoiding these substances improves circularity by reducing hazardous waste and enhancing recirculation in the economic system at end of use.

6.3 Annex 3: List of critical raw materials (European Commission, 2023)

Material	Supply Risk (SR)	Economic Importance (EI)
Criticality threshold	1,0	2,8
Aggregates	0,2	3,2
Aluminium/bauxite	1,2	5,8
Antimony	1,8	5,4
Arsenic	1,9	2,9
Baryte	1,3	3,5
Bentonite	0,4	3,1
Beryllium	1,8	5,4
Bismuth	1,9	5,7
Boron	3,6	3,9
Cadmium	0,2	4,1
Chromium	0,7	7,2
Cobalt	2,8	6,8
Coking coal	1	3,1
Copper	0,1	4
Diatomite	0,3	2,3
Feldspar	1,5	3,2
Fluorspar	1,1	3,8
Gallium	3,9	3,7
Germanium	1,8	3,6
Gold	0,4	2,4
Gypsum	0,6	2,7
Hafnium	1,5	4,3
Helium	1,2	2,9
HREE	5,1	4,2
HREE Dysprosium	5,6	7,8
HREE Erbium	5,6	3,5
HREE Europium	5,6	3,3
HREE Gadolinium	3,3	3,3
HREE Holmium	5,6	3,2
HREE Lutetium	5,6	5
HREE Terbium	4,9	6,4
HREE Thulium	5,6	3,2
HREE Ytterbium	5,6	3,2
HREE Yttrium	3,5	2,9
Hydrogen	0,5	2,9
Indium	0,6	2,6
Iron ore	0,5	7,2
Kaolin clay	0,8	2,8
Krypton	0,7	3,3
Lead	0,1	4,2
Limestone	0,3	3,6
Lithium	1,9	3,9
LREE	3,7	5,9
LREE Cerium	4	4,9
LREE Lanthanum	3,5	2,9
LREE Neodymium	4,5	7,2
Praseodymium	3,2	7
LREE Samarium	3,5	7,7
Magnesite	0,6	3,6
Magnesium	4,1	7,4
Manganese	1,2	6,9
Molybdenum	0,8	6,7
Natural cork	0,9	1,7
Natural graphite	1,8	3,4
Natural Rubber	0,9	6
Natural Teak wood	1,7	2,4
Neon	0,7	3,1

Nickel	0,5	5,7
Niobium	4,4	6,5
Perlite	0,8	2,5
PGM	2,7	7,1
PGM Iridium	3,9	6,4
PGM Palladium	1,5	8,1
PGM Rhodium	2,4	8,6
PGM Ruthenium	3,8	5,5
Phosphate rock	1	6,4
Phosphorus	3,3	4,7
Potash	0,7	6,2
Rhenium	0,5	2,3
Roundwood	0,1	1,2
Sapele wood	1,3	1,6
Scandium	2,4	3,7
Selenium	0,3	4,8
Silica sand	0,3	3,1
Silicon metal	1,3	4,9
Silver	0,8	4,6
Strontium	2,6	6,5
Sulphur	0,3	5
Talc	0,2	3,3
Tantalum	1,3	4,8
Tellurium	0,3	3,8
Tin	0,9	4,5
Titanium	0,5	5,4
Titanium metal	1,6	6,3
Tungsten	1,2	8,7
Vanadium	2,3	3,9
Xenon	0,8	3,1
Zinc	0,2	4,8
Zirconium	0,8	3,5